

Norwegian sheep farmers' perception of the advantages and disadvantages of Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) technologies

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ABSTRACT

Despite enthusiastic industry and policy developments around Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) technology, it is unclear how often the development of new tools is centred around farmers' needs and means. This study aimed to identify the perceived benefits and disadvantages of PLF technology on Norwegian sheep farms. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 24 Norwegian sheep farmers who use one or more PLF tool. Participants were between 35 and 70 years old, were from three Norwegian regions and farmed between 20 and 400 ewes. The most used technologies were GPS collars monitoring sheep location and registration software. Interview transcripts were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis and six themes were identified: Resources and Savings, Gaining Control, The User Experience, The Human-Animal Relationship, Trust in Technology and Stewards of the Land. The identified advantages of technology use were time, energy and economic savings that lightened farmers' cognitive burden, offered an increased sense of control gained through access to new data, an improved relationship between the farmers and their sheep, and an increased ability to preserve their farming lifestyle and the land they farm on. However, these benefits were not unanimously agreed upon, with many participants suggesting that the economic costs outweighed the time and energy savings, that farmers' cognitive burden actually increased, that sellers and digital information could be untrustworthy and that technology posed a risk to the quality of the human-animal relationship. These findings could inform the future development and applications of user-centric PLF products to support the resilience of farming communities.

1. Introduction

Through digital or Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) technology, farms are capturing more data than ever in the hopes of improving decision-making and efficiency (Klerkx et al., 2019; Rotz et al., 2019). New commercial products are developed and marketed to farmers every year (Sundmaeker et al., 2016). Some offer increased efficiency, such as the Internet of Things, while others replace human labour in physically demanding tasks, like milking robots on dairy farms, allowing farmers to attain a more flexible lifestyle (Burton and Farstad, 2020; Hansen, 2015; Wolfert et al., 2017). Others, for example Global Positioning System (GPS) collars for improved surveillance of animals in outdoor systems, offer access to previously unattainable information such as monitoring animal behaviour and location, thus supporting farmers in their decision-making (Neethirajan and Kemp, 2021; Søraa and Vik, 2021; Wolfert et al., 2017). Despite the undeniable advantages technology can

bring, it is unclear how often the development of new tools is centred around farmers' needs and means, rather than the commercial drivers for the technology companies (Lesser, 2014; Wolfert et al., 2017). The users can still face challenges and varied experiences when applying PLF on their farms. These range from practical issues such as rodents damaging new wires installed in barns, to more intangible challenges such as the increased cognitive burdens involved in the managing and interpretation of large datasets (Banhazi et al., 2015; Hostiou et al., 2017a). Additionally, there may be perception issues with the use of technology. For example, sheep products (e.g. wool or meat) from extensive systems are often perceived by consumers as being "natural", a quality which is highly valued, partly because of the freedom the animals have to engage in the same behaviours as their wild relatives (Goddard et al., 2006). It is unclear how accepting consumers will be of high levels of technology being used in these "natural" environments (Wathes et al., 2008). Increased technological developments have been

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central to the restructuring of Norwegian agriculture in the last decades (Logstein, 2016; Torske et al., 2016). Technology has also been reported to be linked to the overall trend of decreasing numbers of Norwegian sheep farms as small operations with low profitability close while the few economically sustainable farms invest in technology to adapt and grow (Lillevoold, 2015; Potthoff and Kopainsky, 2023). Farmers needs must be understood and as users, they should be consulted during the development of new technological tools.

Research has previously been conducted on the factors affecting acceptance of technology by farmers. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) identified perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) as accounting for up to 70 % of variation in farmer behaviour around use and acceptance of technology (Davis et al., 1989; Flett et al., 2004). Normalisation Process Theory (NPT), which was first applied in healthcare, is a framework which helps understand and explain the application of new practices of thinking, enacting and organising work (May et al., 2009). It was originally developed to create a tool that could explain the failure of implementing widely used tools in clinical settings (May et al., 2009). As such, it is well-suited to study the failure to adopt PLF systems in farming industries. A paper applying NPT (May et al., 2009; May and Finch, 2009) to understand British sheep farmers' adoption of PLF technology reported that it helped the authors understand the context preventing adoption (Kaler and Ruston, 2019). They concluded that farmers believed that PLF was costly, difficult to implement, and posed a threat to their role as good stockpeople (Kaler and Ruston, 2019). Another study reported that non-adopters were more likely to believe that governments pressure farmers into adopting technology while adopters had higher information technology literacy and intended to intensify production in the future (Lima et al., 2018). A Norwegian study found that a strong belief in technology, high wage rates and difficulties getting skilled labour led to high adoption of milking robots in certain regions (Hansen, 2015). However, beyond adoption, there are few studies asking about the experiences and satisfaction levels of current users of PLF technology in animal agriculture. This study aims to contribute to this knowledge gap.

The regular use of technology in farming gives rise to ethical debates, notably about the impact it can have on animal welfare and the human-animal relationship (Cornou, 2009; Wathes et al., 2008). Researchers and farmers alike have identified the risk of reducing farmers' contact with their animals, including direct harm through technological malfunction and indirect harms through the further objectification of animals (Hartung et al., 2017; Hostiou et al., 2017b; Schilling et al., 2008; Tuytens et al., 2022). Norwegian studies have also suggested that research into the links between new technology and farmer well-being must be investigated (Hansen and Østerås, 2019), as new digital tools bring new challenges and potentially unfulfilled expectations (Eastwood et al., 2017). Thus, there is a need to understand the lived experiences of farmers using technology to be able to assess the risks and recognize the benefits of PLF. Such findings can inform future development and applications of PLF tools.

The Norwegian sheep industry is an interesting case study to investigate farmers' beliefs about technology. Firstly, many livestock technology tools were invented in Norway, for example Nofence© (Batnfjordsøra, Norway), a virtual fencing system that allows users to draw digital borders that their livestock cannot cross when wearing their collar, and has received previous attention in the literature (Søraa and Vik, 2021), or Findmy (Kvikne, Norway) and Telespor AS (Asker, Norway), two kinds of GPS collars that record the location of sheep at a frequency chosen by the user. Secondly, Norway has a very widely digitised food production system (Søraa and Vik, 2021). For example, Norwegian dairy farmers have the highest rate of adoption of milking robots in the world (Hansen, 2015). Despite anecdotal evidence that many sheep farmers adopt technology at a high rate, the sheep sector is seldom at the foreground in PLF technology discussions in Norway.

This study carried out semi-structured interviews to explore the opinions of Norwegian sheep farmers who are current users of PLF,

specifically seeking to address the research question: What are the perceived advantages and disadvantages of technology use? Using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2019), this study aimed to understand what farmers feel they gain and lose through the use of PLF technologies. This type of study can inform the development and applications of future PLF tools in the small ruminant sector from a farmer perspective. This is important because technology can contribute to Norwegian farmers' future resilience or stress. (Potthoff and Kopainsky, 2023).

2. Methods

Ethical approval was obtained by the University of Edinburgh's Human Ethical Research Committee (HERC_2023_087).

2.1. Interviews with sheep farmers

Farmers were recruited through local sheep farmer organisations *Agritech Cluster-Agriforsk* and *Arktisk kompetansesenter for Sau*, and through the Norwegian Institute for Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO) in September 2023. The selection criteria for participants were that they had more than 20 ewes and used any kind of digital technology in their day to day running of the farm (e.g., Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) wands, automatic feeding systems, GPS collars, etc.). Interviews occurred until saturation was reached. The saturation criteria used was *Code Frequency Count* (Hennink et al., 2017, 2019) meaning that no or few new codes in successive transcripts were identified (Hennink and Kaiser, 2022; Krueger and Casey, 2015). Participants gave written consent after reading a participant information sheet that contained a summary of study objectives, the interview process, data management, anonymity, and confidentiality. These documents were offered in English and Norwegian. Interviews were conducted in English in person at the farmers' homes, workplaces or at public sheep farming events by one researcher. The interviews lasted between 30 and 90 min. Interviews were recorded using a high-resolution WAVE/MP3 recorder (R-09HP by Roland Corporation, Shizuoka, Japan) and an iPhone (iPhone 12 Mini by Apple, Cupertino, USA) as a back-up. A semi-structured interview guide (Supplementary Materials) was used to direct conversations during the interviews. The interview guide consisted of four sections: i) general description of the technology used on farm, ii) the advantages and disadvantages of the technology, iii) their perceptions of technology across the farming industry, and iv) their vision for the future of technology in sheep farming. At the end of the interviews, farmers were asked if there was anything not discussed that they wished to add.

2.2. Participants

In total, 19 interviews were conducted with 23 farmers (during four interviews, we spoke to a couple or an intergenerational team running the farm together). All participants were native Norwegian speakers fluent in English, and interviews were conducted in English. Three counties of Norway were represented: Nordland, Trøndelag and Møre og Romsdal. Participant age ranged from 35 to 70 with a median age of 53. There were seven women and 16 men interviewed. Flock size ranged from 20 to 400 ewes, with a median flock size of 140. Across all the participants, six sheep breeds were farmed: Norwegian White Sheep, Gammalnorsk, Grå Trøndersau, Steigarsau, Norwegian Pelssau and Spælsau.

2.3. Analysis of interview recordings

Interview recordings were transcribed using Otter.ai transcription software (Otter.ai, Mountain View, USA). The transcripts were then validated by the authors. A reflexive thematic analysis using the methodology described by Braun and Clarke (2019) was carried out, using a deductive approach, coding specifically for the advantages and

disadvantages of PLF technology. The deductive approach analyses data with a pre-conceived framework in mind whereas an inductive approach relies on the data themselves to identify themes. Semantic coding was utilised in the first place, which means the analysis of themes was based solely on participants' explicit words shared during the interview. Latent coding was also carried out to complement the semantic coding. Latent coding seeks to draw out themes using a deeper, more interpretive analysis, capturing underlying meaning and shared patterns of meaning (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The analysis was conducted through a constructivist lens that places emphasis on the individual's role in constructing knowledge while acknowledging social influences, past experiences and existing knowledge (Fosnot, 2013; Moallem, 2001). Author assumptions and innate characteristics likely influenced our approach: given that the interviews were conducted by a woman younger than all the participants, who were mostly men, the authors acknowledge the gender and age dynamics at play in her analysis and interpretation of the transcripts. As a researcher, the interviewer may have influenced what participants expressed during the interviews. This may have additionally been affected by the language barrier, as farmers were speaking in their second or third language. The choice to proceed with English language interviews was a practical one, as the researcher available to conduct the relatively time-consuming interviews did not speak Norwegian. Taking notes while reading through the transcripts allowed for salient data extracts to be selected using NVivo 14 software (QSR International, Burlington, USA) and for codes to be extracted. Coded text was organised into themes, which were reviewed and refined. The relationships between themes were mapped and final themes were identified. Interpretation of themes aimed to relate the patterns identified in the data to the broader reality of being a sheep farmer and using technology (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

3. Results

3.1. Technology

Participants spoke about 10 farming technologies across all the interviews. The most popular were collars providing sheep location via GPS through the mobile telephone network or satellites. In order of prevalence among our participants, other technologies included registration software, virtual fencing collars, RFID wands, cameras over lambing pens, Bluetooth connected weigh crates, drones, automatic feeders, ultrasound scanners, and automatic feed mixers.

3.2. Themes

Six themes were extracted from the transcripts. The first was titled *Resources and Savings*, which covered the costs and savings that motivated farmers to purchase and continue using technology (e.g., increased profits) or acted as barriers to implementation or continued use. This encompasses time, energy and economic costs. The second theme identified was *Gaining Control*, which covered the increased sense of control farmers gained through the new information provided by technology and the ways this affected decision-making on farms. The third theme was titled *The User Experience*, and covered farmers' discussions on technical challenges, learning curves, and technology's role in the cognitive burden of farming. The fourth theme, titled *The Human-Animal Relationship*, covered the farmers' views on any impacts that using technology had on their relationship with their sheep. The fifth theme, *Trust in technology*, discussed the varying levels of trust the farmers had in digital data and in technology companies. The sixth theme was titled *Stewards of the Land*, and covered discussions around the role technology plays in allowing farming families to continue their farming activities and in conserving the publicly owned mountain rangeland habitats.

3.2.1. Resources and savings

3.2.1.1. Time and energy costs. The most commonly cited driver behind technology adoption and continued use was a reduction in the amount of time and energy the farmers needed to spend on daily tasks and management activities. Demanding tasks such as recording accurate weights for individual animals at repeated time points, gathering sheep from unfenced mountain pastures and overnight lambing were simplified by technology. This theme was identified through many farmers alluding to the expression "time is money," for example. Overall, the farmers appeared to be looking to improve the efficiency of their work on farm. This is illustrated in the following extracts:

"It's saves us a lot of time. [laughs] It's getting money when you save time." P98

"I don't save money but maybe it's time; from time is money, especially if you have some other work." T47

Despite most farmers agreeing that technology saved them time, a few highlighted that it also creates new tasks that eat up more of a busy farm's time budget, such as when unforeseen work was involved in setting up, updating, or maintaining the technological tools (e.g., programming the signal frequency of GPS collars or updating software). This issue degraded the perceptions of value and savings, primarily because these time costs were unexpected.

"Yeah. So, this [shows another type of collar] about two years old. And you see, this is two batteries and two plugs. And when you have 50, 50 pieces of this is a big job. Put them back in with the screw, testing that it works. See it's on the app. And everything. It's, it's not, it's not quick fix!" W37

A few participants felt like some of the required time and energy to learn all the technology's functionalities was not worth it. These farmers were satisfied only using a limited range of the PLF tools' possible applications. Thus, a lack of time or mental energy to learn acted as a barrier to using PLF technology to its full capacity. This suggests that despite time and energy savings, these two resources will always be in short supply on farms.

"I, of course, I could force myself to learn all these features, but I do not see enough good things to take the investment to learn it." Q61

3.2.1.2. Economic costs. High economic cost was the most cited barrier to purchasing technological tools. Some farmers who already owned equipment, such as GPS collars that require upfront payments and yearly subscriptions, were satisfied with the time savings they incurred but dissatisfied with the high economic price they had to pay. Many farmers addressed this issue by only putting GPS collars on some of their sheep, for example.

"It's too expensive to put it [GPS collar] on all of them. Because say, the cost: around 2000 kroner invest in each of them. [...] And then they have this annual cost, which is more than \$200 per unit. So, it's, it costs a bit more to be using it on all of them. And so, we tried to use it on those [sheep] who we think would be difficult to find in, in autumn." T47

However, many farmers described economic benefits that stemmed from their technology use. The time and energy saved through PLF tools allowed some farmers to pursue other work which provided additional income. Although few farmers had quantified the financial gain, they nonetheless perceived PLF technology as having benefitted them financially. The few farmers that had carried out cost-benefit assessments reported that technology was crucial to creating additional income, as illustrated in the following extract.

“Yeah, because I do other jobs too. And every hour spent on the sheep cost me. So, every time every hour spared, I’m earning 550 kroner. Okay. Plus, tax.” Q34

Thanks to the technology, farmers who owned automatic feeders or feed mixers said they saw an increase in their lamb weights, and therefore in their profits, compared to past years. However, none had calculated whether the cost of technological tools had been paid off by this increase in meat profit.

“So now, we are delivering, now really going to come out at 23.5 kilos in meat. [...] So that is very good. It’s the biggest in my time. That’s great. Yes.” R63

Time and energy savings along with potential economic benefits were described as major drivers of technology use. However, these benefits were tempered by reports of the important time, energy and monetary investments needed to reap these benefits.

3.2.2. Gaining Control

Most participants expressed added control as one of the reasons why they liked and used technology. They felt the extra information provided about their sheep, such as location, weight, or genetic history, enabled them to make informed decisions about their business, increasing their sense of control over their success.

“It means more to have control and know where they are and know that I can go on long weekend without having trouble. Yeah, yeah. So, it has helped us a lot, I think. [...] This is probably the main, the main thing for sheep farmers: to have control.” E99

Predator attacks were often cited as situations where technology could increase farmers’ control, where not much else could. Collars that provide farmers with their sheep’s location were particularly useful in identifying predator attacks as they can flag unexpected movement patterns (e.g., dispersing, running many kilometres). Farmers concluded that these metrics indicate a likely predator attack or observation of a predator by the flock. Some farmers reported using location data to make breeding decision to protect their flock against future predators by encouraging tight flock structures. Based on the GPS maps, they bred from ewes that stayed close together in safe areas and did not breed from or culled ewes that separated from the flock often.

“We can also see if there, already if the flock is spreading, you can see it: the predators. So, it’s, that’s good” C42

“So, then I get the clue of when they are leaving and if the lambs are worth having as, as ewes because if they walk, in June then they walk away directly out of the grazing area and the lambs are not interesting for, for breeding. But if they are walking [away from the desired area] in late August and first of, the first week of September then they have been all summer in the, in the area so, they, they would probably be hefted to this area, to use an English expression.” F50

Farmers found the extra information interesting, useful, and in some cases, even fun. They felt more informed making breeding, feeding, time management and staffing decisions. A handful of farmers shared stories of saving individual sheep from death thanks to GPS collars, which is a good example of how their increased sense of control can be manifested.

3.2.3. The User Experience

Across the wide range of technologies mentioned by our participants, e.g., GPS collars, virtual fencing and drones, most farmers found the tools easy to use. Even farmers who self-identified as “not a computer guy” found they did not have steep learning curves and were able to start using them quickly.

“Oh no, I’m not ... very ... I’m not especially interested in phone and I don’t have ... I had [mimes a flip phone] for a long time. I bought

that in 2007. And I didn’t get this [points to smartphone] before my daughter changed. So, I, I’m not very interested in, but [virtual fencing tool] is easy. As we used to tell people: if I can make it, everyone can make it. [laughs]” M66

Farmers sometimes found it “fun” and “cool” to be able to see where their sheep were, despite being miles away up a mountain through the use of GPS collars, for example. Many enjoyed sharing the new information they obtained with lay people and others who had little to no responsibility on the farm, such as older relatives.

“I didn’t believe they walked those distances every day. As they do. They move a lot more around that I think. And now I know where they sleep at night. So, it’s, it’s funny to see.” I69

Some farmers specified that given the technology’s costs, they expected durability and consistency. Durability was defined as every component resisting the rough, dirty, and wet conditions on farm over significant periods of time. Consistency referred to the farmers’ desire for a constant, seamless delivery of services over several years, without regular changes or updates to the system. Farmers shared many instances where both of these expectations were not met and instead, they had to address various technical shortcomings. This sometimes involved hours on the phone with customer support or having to completely stop using a tool due to a fault, both of which are described below in relation to collars that were purchased. Farmers were often disappointed because durability and consistency were seen as basic necessities for farming technology.

“The real technology, the GSM and GPS, the server they are using? That cause, it makes problems, big problems. [...] They have no control on nice signal, they have none control. But of course, they should be more clever with a server, they have big server problem last year. When they don’t work, you don’t know where the sheep is. Yeah, then you can use nine days to find it. [...] So, it’s: pray, be angry, call supplier, shout at them.” W37

“I use [virtual fencing collars] too, 30 sheep up in the mountains. [...] Because of a production failure, the metal clamp that was into the plastic was too soft. And the first year, I said: sure, you just press them together. And I did that. And last year I ... the same problem! And then I called: oh, what can you change? No, it’s like, just the way it is. And that was the answer. Yeah. Could you have to? No, you have to just accept it. And in two years, you have to buy a new [one] anyway!” Q34

Farmers’ perception of the technology’s effect on their cognitive burden was mixed. Some noted that PLF tools reduced cognitive and emotional burdens, for example, by reducing confrontations with neighbours thanks to digital fencing, reducing anxiety over leaving the farm for holidays by providing sheep location information through GPS, or helping keep the sheep organised in groups without any paperwork or memorization thanks to a RFID weighing system. On the other hand, some farmers pointed out that the huge amount of additional information that was now accessible anytime and anywhere resulted in added anxiety. The pressure to act on this new information and to always be connected increased their cognitive burden.

“It’s sorted there. So, I just, when I go up [in the barn] and, and are doing the work. It’s already ... the brain work are (sic) done. It’s just so when you’re standing with the dog and the sheep and it get messy ... So, I can do that. I love this. [...] even if I have a high capacity, it’s limited. Yeah. At some point. Yeah. So, I like to work with the sheep. But it comes also with a cost. Yeah. So, the time and work and energy I use there. I doesn’t ... I can’t use somewhere else. I can’t use all ... sometimes it lowers my battery. And so [with technology] I have more energy.” Q34

“But in a way, you, when you have all this information, you also feel you’re never free. Just, oh no ... It can come in at night time or 11 in the evening.” B42

Similarly, to the theme of resource savings discussed above (3.2.1), farmers reports seem to indicate that while their cognitive burden was alleviated in regards to some tasks, new tasks were created and required their mental energy.

3.2.4. *The human-animal relationship*

When asked about their relationship with their sheep, many farmers felt their improved access to information and increased control improved this relationship. Knowing more about their sheep improved their ability to care for them, both as individuals and as a flock. This increased knowledge led the farmers to feel closer, or more connected to their sheep. As illustrated in the following extract, it is clear that for many farmers, control and a good relationship with their sheep were linked.

“Maybe, I think to the better because I have better control with my sheep. Because I have them in, in groups and I know why they are in this group, because it’s the electronic RFID that tell me that they are together. And the scanning of lambs: and I checked more on the one [ewe] with three [lambs] than the one with one lamb in the winter. I think it’s a better connection.” I23

The use of wearable PLF tools such as GPS collars or virtual fencing collars often enabled farmers to gain more individual insights on each of their sheep. Where prior to using the collars, the sheep would have been managed as a flock, they were now visible individuals on a map. This seemed to strengthen the connection between the farmer and each sheep, as reflected by the following quote.

“I have names of some of my ewes. And they who have names, they get the bells [collars]. [...] Of course, when you see that it’s: oh, there goes Aragon goes to London. So perhaps, maybe I have a relationship with them before, but perhaps it’s more close? Yeah. Because I know.” C42

However, a few farmers acknowledged a possible negative spill over effect that comes with the control PLF offers. For example, some noted a possible disconnect between farmers and animals. These claims were more anecdotal or supposition than personal experience. These same farmers stated their perceived responsibility to the animals meant that they would not allow technology to distance them from their animals. Only one farmer admitted that through their use of virtual fencing collars, they were likely checking on their flock less than they previously did, or less than they should.

“I know [some]one who got the camera in her house. Yeah, when lambing lambs comes in spring, she sits in and driving the camera around and see Oh, that’s good. It’s good. She wasn’t in in your barn. [...] No, no, I don’t like that. You want to be, I want to be there. And if it is something wrong, you had to stay there and observe through all time and get in when, when you’ve got help. And then you can save a lot of animals.” C28

Although technology seemed to have the ability to bring farmers closer to their sheep, the risks of it negatively impacting the human-animal relationship were acknowledged and actively prevented by many.

3.2.5. *Trust in technology*

When their expectations of time and energy savings were not met and the costs were not outweighed by the benefits, several farmers reported a lack of trust in technology companies, resulting in indefinite termination of product use. According to farmers, it was not possible to win back this trust once it was lost. Farmers trusted sellers more when they knew the company founders had ties to farming. Several

participants mentioned companies getting sold to far-flung software companies, leading to reduced customer support. A few people felt wronged by companies that had gone bankrupt and left them with boxes full of unusable equipment.

“because we used to have [Company A]. But they went, the company went bankrupt and we didn’t trust them anymore. So, we stopped using it. We had 47 of those. [...] It worked very good for the first year. But then they had some problems and couldn’t give any support or anything. So, it was just very bad. And people have bought many items on it! Yes. So [...] This is the same people so we don’t trust them. It cost too much too. So, I think they tried to make a connection between mother and lambs. But we haven’t try that.” I58

Farmers not trusting technology to make accurate measurements acted as a hurdle to further PLF technology implementation. They were fearful or sceptical of relying on the information given by the digital tools. The more technologically literate farmers we spoke to referred to colleagues and acquaintances who didn’t trust technology, while some of the farmers we interviewed self-identified as sceptics despite using the technology regularly.

“Many farmers are afraid of the grain feeding system, they’ll think it’s too expensive and too advanced and really difficult. [...] Okay, everything with a computer in it is dangerous. [...] It’s, I think it’s a mix of many things. But many farmers are practical guys. They want to use a hammer or a bench or a saw. Something like that.” Q61

Trust in digital tools partly explained technology use, but this trust could be lost if the sellers did not provide acceptable levels of support.

3.2.6. *Stewards of the land*

Several farmers were happy to incur the high costs of technology because it ensured the family farm would be taken over by the next generation and that their lifestyle would carry on. Integrating technology was seen as keeping young people interested and invested in farming, while allowing them to pursue other revenue streams with the time it saved. This is illustrated in the following extract, where a farmer describes his hope for the future of their family farm now that he had invested in an automatic feeder and a new barn.

“I think when my son has taken over, when he is feeding in the morning, he can just touch button and then they eat and [he can] go to work.” R63

Participants discussed how technology had specific benefits for older farmers in securing the longevity of their farming operation. For example, auto-draft machines and automatic feeders could reduce manual labour, protecting older farmers’ physical health and lengthening their contributions to the farm. Some farmers stated that if it wasn’t for the technology, they would have quit farming, saying things like “I really can’t imagine the life as a farmer without it”.

“I think this weight [crate] which we have bought, it will save our body because this sheep will learn to go in a row and into the weight. And we will “beep” in computer and we don’t have to do all the with our arms and shoulders and it will save our ... I think it will be good for us. Yeah. And that’s important because [...] we are not getting younger. But for younger farmer it will be better than that. They can live longer. Yes. It is very important to think about health. Many farmers are very tired when they’re getting 60 and that is too early. Because they are not old. Definitely so, I think technology is good for us, to help us and we will use it if we can.” I58

The view that farming is an “old” profession and incompatible with technology seemed to be seeping in from the urban public, who can think of farmers as backwards country people, cut-off from the world. But some of the participants identified their use of technology as an opportunity to challenge this view and share their high-tech reality with the public. By doing so, they felt they could ensure that the farming

lifestyle is recognised as central to society. Farmers knew that there were fewer and fewer of them as farm numbers have decreased across Norway. They saw PLF technology as a tool to support people who are still farming.

“I would have started with [GPS collars]. Outside. Yeah, because of we are less and less farmers. The area’s the same. The sheep (sic) use the area, so you got more and more area to look in every year. So that one [farmer] stops, that one stops. So, I would have started with [GPS collars] or something that could help me in finding them.” R76

A handful of participants highlighted the role that sheep farmers play as stewards of the land. In most of Norway, sheep graze in publicly owned mountain rangeland in the summer. This land is not used for many other purposes and contains endangered plant and animal species. Sheep farmers saw their use of these grazing areas as an act of conservation, especially protecting them from summer home developments.

“I mean, it’s right. To, that sheep is going on the mountain in the ... it’s best for people and best for, for animal.” Z44

One of the benefits of technology use was its capacity to empower farmers in maintaining their family’s rural lifestyle and thereby protecting the landscapes in which they work.

4. Discussion

4.1. Advantages of PLF technology use

4.1.1. Savings and economic benefits

The utility of PLF for reducing the expenditure of physical and mental resources proved invaluable for some farmers. Indeed, time-saving is one of the principal objectives of using technology in most contexts, including agriculture (Bonabana-Wabbi, 2002; Mwangi and Kariuki, 2015) and it is one of the principal expectations of farmers adopting technology (Devitt, 2018). Naturally, saving physical energy is important as farm work is physically arduous and farmers are at increased risk of many musculoskeletal disorders and injuries (Walker-Bone and Palmer, 2002). Economically, the structure of rural Norway is changing as new markets become accessible and diversifying farm incomes becomes the norm (Eikeland and Lie, 1999). Since 2017, the Norwegian sheep population has declined by 12 % and many farms have gone out of business (Knutsen, 2020). The farmers that remain have been faced with reduced profitability (Knutsen, 2020). Within this financial context, increased profits or savings thanks to technology is an important advantage. There is evidence from around the world that technology adoption can help revenue enhancement and production efficiency through diversification and off-farm income (Eikeland and Lie, 1999; Fernandez-Cornejo et al., 2007; Morris et al., 2017; Søraa and Vik, 2021).

Interestingly, the farmers in our study had only rarely calculated the exact economic advantages they’d gained through PLF technology. This aligns with past research noting that farmers report knowing little about gains and profits (Kaler and Green, 2013). This was presented as due to a lack of record-keeping, which the farmers did not prioritise (Kaler and Green, 2013). A survey of English and Welsh farmers similarly found that 62 % of respondents had problems with record-keeping and paperwork (Simkin et al., 1998). Even though it may partly explain their findings around record-keeping, these older studies may not have taken into account the fact that levels of dyslexia are higher in farming than in the average population, since this is a more recent topic of discussion (Smith et al., 2020). Another hypothesis is that not examining their farming practice through an economic lens is a reaction to the low level of control held by farmers over their circumstances: they do not keep a close eye on the finances of their operation because it is out of their hands anyway. They may feel they cannot control the large impacts external forces such as weather, fluctuating markets and government regulations can have on their profits (Lunner Kolstrup et al., 2013). Or it

may be that their motivation for farming is not only financial, as suggested by reviews of British and Norwegian farmers’ attitudes (Garforth and Rehman, 2005; Kvakkestad et al., 2015), which indicate farmers see their contributions to society as a public good. So, although technology has high potential to save farmers time and money, farmers in this study rarely provided exact figures.

4.1.2. Increased control

A major benefit of PLF technology is increased control for farmers, as noted in the present study and reflected in case studies of specific technological tools. A study of Norwegian farmers’ adoption of Internet of Things technology reported that increased control was one of its perceived advantages (Lillestrøm, 2021), as did a study on digital fencing for goat farmers in Norway (Søraa and Vik, 2021). Similar research on British sheep farmers found that PLF tools that empower them to be in control might encourage uptake (Kaler and Ruston, 2019).

The role PLF technology plays in increasing control around predator management was discussed by almost every farmer interviewed. When they spoke about technology and predators, it was mostly hypothetical, meaning they had many ideas about its potential for reducing the impact of predators, but no concrete actions were taken on their farms. This interest in using technology to manage predators may reflect interest from the research and policy worlds. Many studies model or simulate predator attacks to extract technological data that could identify real attacks (Manning et al., 2014; Virgilio et al., 2018). In 2004 and 2011, the Norwegian parliament came to two decisions, referred to by the public as the Carnivore Settlements. These settlements aimed to reconcile continued sustainable livestock production and the maintenance of viable carnivore populations (Strand, 2021). There is no doubt that sheep farmers have therefore been inundated with media and government messaging about predators over the last 20 years. In fact, a few participants commented that this was a government priority and this is reflected in studies of Norwegian land management policies (Strand, 2021; Strand et al., 2019). Farmers have so little control over whether a predator is present or not, that technology seemed to offer them a sense of security. As such, although there is agreement around the potential for PLF technology to help manage predators, current benefits are difficult to prove.

4.1.3. Alleviating the cognitive burden

Technology was beneficial in reducing cognitive and emotional burdens on farmers, such as reducing anxiety and the burdens placed on memory (e.g., having to remember pedigree information or weights). Research from across the world has shown that farmers suffer from navigating the cognitive burden (e.g. data management, decision-making) of their work mostly alone, and face stigma and a lack of support services if this isolation leads to mental health challenges (Deffontaines, 2014; Eastwood et al., 2023; Fuller et al., 2000; Lunner Kolstrup et al., 2013). In fact, farming is listed as one of the 10 most stressful jobs in the USA (Sauter et al., 1999). Past research has found technology can also free more time to spend on other tasks, increasing connection with animals and other staff, helping with decision-making and reducing the cognitive burden of farmers (Eastwood et al., 2023; Hostiou et al., 2023; Nazareno and Schiff, 2021). This echoes our finding that technology freed up time to watch the sheep, which increased the farmers’ feeling of connection with them. Our participants similarly reported feeling more confident in their decision-making thanks to PLF tools. Indeed, a reduction of the cognitive burden appeared as a benefit for the uptake of the technology.

4.1.4. Improving the human-animal relationship

Research on British sheep farmers found that tools that empower farmers to be in control and that do not affect the human-animal relationship might encourage uptake of PLF (Kaler and Ruston, 2019). Participants in our study discussed how the technology increased their control and therefore benefitted their relationship with the sheep. This

perceived improvement in the human-animal relationship was interesting, as many studies of PLF have highlighted its deleterious effects on the human-animal relationship (Buller et al., 2020; Cornou, 2009). Most farmers interviewed in our study seemed aware of this risk but did not feel it applied to them because contact with their sheep was a priority. A previous study reported that pig and broiler farmers are similarly aware of the risk that PLF would reduce their human-animal contacts, but make a point of continuing to directly observe their animals because they know the technology does not replace the farmer's knowledge (Hartung et al., 2017). In the current study, our farmers provided several explanations for safeguarding their relationship with their sheep: some thought having a good relationship with their animals reduced sheep stress at handling, while others explicitly stated it is impossible to be a good farmer while not being in contact with your animals. Some farmers simply enjoyed taking the time to observe their sheep, leading to feelings of increased connection with their flock. The literature on human-animal interactions and their impact on animal welfare tends to agree with these farmers' points. Sheep can recognize regular caretakers' faces and remember them for up to 2 years (Kendrick et al., 2001; Knolle et al., 2017). This suggests that regular contact can help create a positive human-animal relationship (Rault et al., 2020). Our findings would suggest that technology can sometimes increase contact opportunities by freeing up time. Additionally, one of the benefits of a PLF approach described by Berckmans (2017) is that it allows for individual management of animals that would previously have been managed as a flock where the only metrics available would have been flock averages. This shift has potential to improve the human-animal relationship through increased access to individual animal information, as was often identified by our participants.

4.1.5. Ensuring farm lifestyle sustainability

Many participants' investment in technology to encourage the next generations to continue farming reflects an implicit link they made between youth and technology. Interestingly, a previous study did not find that age affected Electronic Identification (EID) adoption for flock management and highlighted the lack of a clear link between age and technology adoption in the agricultural literature (Lima et al., 2018). Similarly, our participants' age did not affect their levels of PLF adoption. In fact, the second oldest farmer was the one who had purchased the most types of PLF tools and the youngest only used one type. There is some evidence from outside agriculture that age influences adoption of technology by affecting the level of importance accorded to it when making decisions (Morris and Venkatesh, 2000). Other farmers took a different approach and invested in technology in support of their own physical and mental health into old age, ensuring the longevity of their business and lifestyle. Evidence suggests that Norwegian farmers see their role in society as providers of safe, high-quality food (Kvakkestad et al., 2015). The present study's findings touch on this topic, with farmers noting that farm numbers in Norway are steadily declining, partly as a result of post-war policies (Shucksmith and Rønningen, 2011), meaning the workload of remaining farmers and their responsibilities have increased. Farmers see PLF technology as supporting them in facing this new challenge. Future research could explore further the role technology plays in the way farmers see themselves within society.

Although only briefly brought up by a few participants, technology was sometimes seen as a tool that supported sheep farmers in their role as stewards of the Norwegian *utmark*. This word can be roughly translated to the rangeland or the outfields, and refers to the publicly owned unfenced pastures that are used by livestock farmers to graze their animals. It consists of bare mountains, mountain forests, productive coniferous forests, ravines, coastal heathlands, and many more ecosystems (Rekdal and Angeloff, 2021). The estimated value of the feed these areas offer, if replaced by equivalent quantities of concentrate, would be 3.8 billion Norwegian kroner (Rekdal and Angeloff, 2021). Adequate grazing management of the *utmark* is seen as a priority to protect the

farming industry but also the cultural landscape and biodiversity (Rekdal and Angeloff, 2021). In a way, some farmers see themselves as guardians of these areas. They feel responsible for maintaining the "lights in the windows" in small rural communities linked to the *utmark*, as suggested in a study of rural sustainability in Norway (Shucksmith and Rønningen, 2011). The present study's findings indicate that there may be potential for PLF technology to benefit farmers in their preservation of this land and of their lifestyle.

4.2. Disadvantages of PLF technology use

4.2.1. Time and economic costs

European livestock farmers are constantly under huge amounts of pressures (Hartung et al., 2017). Not only do they face significant and mounting economic pressure, but they must answer societal demands, notably: providing food security, food safety, food affordability, environmental protection and animal welfare (Hartung et al., 2017). It is no surprise that farmers feel they do not have time to fully explore the potential of PLF technology, even if it promises to alleviate some of these pressures. This counterbalances the time and energy-saving advantage of PLF tools, so perhaps any time savings are reallocated to new tasks rather than freeing up more time. Farmers spoke about the high economic costs of technology as its most important disadvantage. Norwegian sheep farmers face low profitability and economic uncertainty, so it is unsurprising that the price of a new tool is a major concern (Lillevoll, 2015; Logstein, 2016). A case study of EID uptake in British farmers found similar priorities among their participants, with 66 % of farmers agreeing or strongly agreeing with the statement "The cost of equipment is important to my decision to use EID recording for farm management" (Lima et al., 2018). However, as has been noted in previous studies of technology adoption, strictly economic models cannot account for the complexity of farmers' motivations and behaviours (Flett et al., 2004).

4.2.2. Increasing the cognitive burden

While there is evidence that technology can lighten the physical burden of farmers, including the present study's findings, it also creates a new task for them, e.g. supervising the tools to ensure they act as desired (Hostiou et al., 2017a; Lunner Kolstrup et al., 2013). Further work is also created when machine breakage occurs, leading to more stress (Lunner Kolstrup et al., 2013). As with time costs discussed above, it is important to acknowledge that the cognitive burden that is alleviated by PLF technology is not entirely removed, but rather shifted to new areas. Previous research on the topic has identified these new challenges around the cognitive burden, such as the steep adaptation curve involved in learning PLF technology functions – which our participants touched upon – as well as the handling of the huge amounts of data produced by the technology (Eastwood et al., 2023; Nazareno and Schiff, 2021). If technology is presented as a tool to improve farmer and animal welfare, then scenarios where farmers inundated with data become disconnected from their animals must be avoided.

4.2.3. Worsening the human-animal relationship

Thankfully, our findings seem to indicate that most farmers are aware of the risk of a deteriorating human-animal relationship though this doesn't mean that concerns can be entirely dismissed. Valid warnings about reducing human-animal interactions to unpleasant management procedures such as castration, for example, are discussed in the ethical debate around PLF (Cornou, 2009; Hostiou et al., 2017b). Seeing as farmers seem to prioritise contact with their animals in order to mitigate these risks, it may be that the human-animal relationship and animal welfare are more threatened by indirect harms through PLF technology (Tuytens et al., 2022). Examples of indirect harms include building a barn around the technology's needs rather than the animals' or a shift in the moral status of animals in society brought on by further objectification through PLF technology use (Tuytens et al., 2022). To monitor this, future research could examine intergenerational

differences in the human-animal relationships on farms, since there seem to be intergenerational differences in technology use (Verma and Garg, 2022; Volkom et al., 2014).

4.2.4. Untrustworthy sellers and tools

The concern that development of PLF technologies will occur at the cost of farmers' time and money has previously been highlighted in the literature (Wathes et al., 2008). These authors raise the question of whether sufficient market research is being done by engineers to truly meet farmers' needs (Wathes et al., 2008). The present study's findings suggest that products are in fact still being developed at the farmer's expense. If the products do not deliver on their promises, farmers lose trust in these companies. Conversely, a survey of broiler, pig and dairy farmers found that farmers receiving sufficient support from the providers held a positive view towards the PLF systems (Hartung et al., 2017). This finding was reaffirmed in the present study by farmers who were satisfied with the level of support they received from the PLF companies and were equally satisfied with the tools. In these circumstances, trust is linked to the degree of confidence, predictability, faith, or cooperation that prevails in the provider-user relationship (Kasperson et al., 1992). For example, many farmers mentioned their refusal to engage with a company after bankruptcy even though it was back on its feet under another name because of the lack of support and cooperation that was offered as the first iteration of the company was closing its doors.

Most farmers interviewed were enthusiastic adopters of technology, but they spoke about others who did not believe that technology could make more accurate measurements than humans. Looking at mistrust through a Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) lens would suggest that farmers who have a negative attitude towards PLF are much less likely to adopt it or show intention to adopt it, compared to those who have a more positive attitude (Ajzen, 1991). TPB has been applied in a range of disciplines and outlines that intention to perform behaviours can be accurately predicted by attitudes towards the behaviour, subjective norms and perception of behavioural control (Ajzen, 1991; Morris and Venkatesh, 2000). Research suggests that distrust in technology acts as an inhibitor of acceptance (Parasuraman, 2000). For example, EID adoption as a management tool among farmers was affected by their level of readiness as measured by the Technology Readiness Index (TRI) (Lima et al., 2018). The TRI is a standardised measure of consumer readiness to embrace new technologies (Lima et al., 2018). To increase trust and motivation, one must remove knowledge and skill barriers (Lima et al., 2018).

5. Conclusion

In this study, six themes (Resources and Savings, Gaining Control, The User Experience, The Human-Animal Relationship, Trust in Technology and Stewards of the Land) were extracted from interviews with Norwegian sheep farmers to understand the benefits and disadvantages of using PLF technology on sheep farms. Study participants discussed the advantages offered by PLF technology, which included time, energy and economic savings that went hand in hand with a lightning of farmers' cognitive burden, an increased sense of control gained through access to new data, an improved relationship between the farmers and their sheep, and an increased ability to preserve their farming lifestyle and the land they farm on. These benefits were not unanimously agreed upon, with many participants suggesting that the economic costs actually outweighed the time and energy savings, that the cognitive burden risked being increased, that sellers and digital information were untrustworthy and that technology posed a risk to the quality of the human-animal relationship. This study's findings contribute to the understanding of how farmers use PLF technology and how they perceive the ethical debates around animal welfare that arise from PLF applications. The farmer descriptions of their likes and dislikes around PLF technology could inform a farmer-centric approach to future

technological developments that may encourage uptake.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michelle C. Reeves: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lise Grøva:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Lesley Jessiman:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Cathy M. Dwyer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

No generative AI or AI-assisted technologies were used in the writing of this manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2025.103684>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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